

Experimental Film Class: Watbangkapom School, Samut Songkhram

Areerut J.

Abstract—Experimental Film Class Project is supported by the Institute for Research and Development at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. This project is purported to provide academic and professional services to improve the quality standards of the community and locals in accordance with the mission of the university, which is to improve and expand knowledge for the community and to develop and transfer such knowledge and professions to the next generation. Eventually, it leads to sustainable development because the development of human resources is deemed as the key for sustainable development. Moreover, the Experimental Film Class is an integral part of the teaching of film production at Suan Sunandha International School of Art (SISA). By means of giving opportunities to students for participation in projects by sharing experience, skill and knowledge and participation in field activities, it helps students in the film production major to enhance their abilities and potentials as preparation for their readiness in the marketplace. Additionally, in this class, we provide basic film knowledge, screenwriting techniques, editing and subtitles including uploading videos on social media such as YouTube and Facebook for the participant students.

Keywords—Experimental Film Class, Watbangkapom School, Participant students, Basic of film production, Film Workshop.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, films and movies are deemed as essential for popular media since they reach every generation. They can be made to include knowledge and provide food-for-thought as well. Today, short film competitions are popular among teenagers, students and people with the skills and knowledge in film production. Hence it has become very competitive. Additionally, posting, sharing video clips or short films on social media and YouTube has also become very popular among the youth as well.

Associate professor Piyakul Laowansiri from the Faculty of Journalism and Mass Communications at Thammasat University states that “movies are the most important and powerful media of all, as they can be a tool for providing knowledge and changing views. For example, Russia used film in converting political views and America uses film to sell their culture; also including Korea where there is a policy of supporting film production as it is deemed as useful media” [1]. Also, associate professor Raksarn Wiwatsin-Udom from the Faculty of Communication Arts, Chulalongkorn University supports the view that “Film is like a mirror of society. The film presents how the society is. Moreover, film

is like a light to the society and people.” [1]

The project manager realizes such importance hence, the establishment of the Experimental Film Class. It is in hope that the participant students will develop themselves to become film producers in the near future. This is also considered to be a great opportunity to increase skills, improve knowledge in creating works, and develop skills in clearly conveying the story in accordance with the purpose or the desire that they want transmitted through the film. Nonetheless, the most important thing is that the participants can have a space to learn and improve their skill to become a professional. The pilot school of this project is Watbangkapom School which is a school located in Amphawa District, Samut Songkhram Province [2].

II. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To encourage the participant students to gain knowledge, skill and creativity in film production.
- 2) To promote participant students to develop skill in digital camera filming technique.
- 3) Learn how to work as a team and working with others.

III. PROJECT PROCEEDINGS

The Experimental Film Class composes of the instruction and lecturing including training to the participant students. It will help encouraging and developing digital camera filming technique skill and creativity in screen writing by the following proceedings;

1. Meeting with the school for its cooperation with the project.
2. Publicizing the project.
3. Recruiting the participant.
4. Contacting the trainer and providing materials in training.
5. Arranging the training of basic film production.
6. Evaluation of the project's outcome.

IV. MATERIALS AND KNOWLEDGE

The production of film is required not only science; process and knowledge in terms of skill and technique in filming, but also knowledge in arts. The knowledge in arts is a transmission of imagination through story, dialogue, camera angle and editing. And it also provides students with an opportunity to express their potential in creating work through film; from screen writing, planning the filming, filming. Hence, it is a way for students to express themselves, share their idea to others and transfer the idea into film script,

A. J. is with Suan Sunandha International School of Art (SiSA), Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (phone: 662-160-1350; fax: 662-160-1351; e-mail: areerut.ja@ssru.ac.th).

including know how to work with others. There were some topics we shared in the class:

1. Role and importance of film: providing entertaining and relaxing sources to the society, providing food of thought to the viewers, providing a reflection of the society, persuading and changing behavior of people in the society, source of income and Economic Value Added. [3]
2. Invention before the occurrence of film: The first camera of Edison is called Kinetograph (Peep-Show Projector). [4]

Fig. 1 Kinetograph

3. Type of shot: ECU (Extreme Close Up) is for emphasizing on a detail and catching the mood of the character. CU (Close Up) is size of object in the picture is smaller than ECU and we can see the whole face. [4]

Fig. 2 ECU shot

Fig. 3 CU shot

4. The Traditional Story Plotline: we can divide into 3 acts are Act 1 – Beginning – Set up (story, character, dramatic premise and situation) Act2 – Middle – the confrontation (obstacle after obstacle, Midpoint and point) Act3 – Ending – The resolution (climax and Denouement). [5]

Fig. 4 Plot Chart: The Traditional Story Plotline

Fig. 5 Students from SISA share basic knowledge and skill in film production to the participant students before on-field activity

Fig. 6 Students from SISA participate in filming with all of participant students

Fig. 7 Participant students learn how to edit video

V. OUTCOME OF THE PROJECT

The project manager arranged questionnaires to assess the outcome of the project. And the outcome from the participants (30 students) is as seen in the below graph:

Fig. 8 The outcome of the project: from indicators:

- 1) Knowledge and understanding of the participants gaining from the project
- 2) Satisfaction of the participants from the project
- 3) Adaptation and extension of knowledge by participants in the future.

VI. CONCLUSION

The outcome of this project shows that results of outcome are higher than aim. At the beginning, the project manager expect to get 80% from each indicators: 1) Knowledge and understanding of the participants gaining from the project 2) Satisfaction of the participants from the project 3) Adaptation and extension of knowledge by participants in the future as blue graph but a summary of outcome get 90% for knowledge and understanding of the participants gaining from the project, 95% for Satisfaction of the participants from the project and 90% for Adaptation and extension of knowledge by participants in the future as red graph. It seems that this project is successful and gets good feedback from participants.

VII. PROBLEMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Problems

- I. The readiness of the participants; basic knowledge and skill, including the creativity in film production are low.
- II. Equipment and programs are not convenient to the participants i.e. no digital camera or mobile-phone camera that can video-tape; and the available editing program cannot be applied and the capacity of computer RAM is low causing difficulty in using editing program.
- III. Low on participation because during the break from school, most students go back to their hometown.

B. Recommendations

- I. Examining the readiness by talking to the participants and clearly identifying the participants, increasing the training period.
- II. Examining the readiness of the equipment and programs before the actual training date; the organizer must do the examination by themselves with cooperation of teachers and staffs in the community.
- III. Publication in advance so that students can plan about the participation including contacting the school for information concerning the period of school break.

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Areerut J. graduated bachelor of art majoring in Radio and Television broadcasting technology at Faculty of Mass communication of technology, Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi in 2004 with First class honour. She graduated Master of art in Documentary Practice at Brunel University, United Kingdom in 2011. During her study in United Kingdom, she is working in media and event organizer as freelance. She used to be a stage manager for Thai Festival Event that take place in Warwick and were a main camera in NUVO Live in London. After she came back from United Kingdom, She was offered to be a public relation and communications manager at Habitat Thailand. She currently works in media production event and a lecturer in department of film production at Suan Sunandha International School of Art, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand.